

SYED MUHAMMAD AL-HUSAINI GESÜDARĀZ

(721-825/1321-1422)

Mohammad Suleman Siddiqi

LIFE

SYED MUHAMMAD AL-HUSAINI GESUDARAZ, a well-known Chishtī saint of the Deccan, was twenty-second in the line of descent from the Prophet of Islam. 'Abdu'l Hasan al-Jundi from whom he claims¹ descent in the twelfth generation arrived in Delhi from Khurāsān. He was laid to rest in the premises of *Masjid-e Anār* (Delhi).¹ The ancestors of our saint were popularly known as *Sādāt-i darāz gīsū*² (Syeds with long locks) in Khurāsān. His grandfather Syed 'Alī and his father Syed Yusuf al-Husainī *alias* Syed Rāja, author of *Tuhfatu'n Naṣā'ih* and *Mathnavi-e Rāja*, were both disciples of the great saint Shaykh Nizām al-Dīn Auliya of Delhi.³

Syed Muḥammad Husainī Gesūdarāz was born on 4th Rajab 721 A.H./ 30th July, 1321 A.D. in Delhi and spent his childhood in that city and in Daulatabād. Both these cities were then great centres of Muslim political, social, cultural and religious activities in Asia. Delhi was not only the capital of the Tughlaq dynasty but was also the abode of countless scholars, saints, administrators and artists. There were nearly two thousand *ribats*, *khānqāhs* in Delhi⁴ and the disciples of Shaykh Nizām al-Dīn 'Auliya who earned renown for their piety and learning like Shaykh Nasīr al-Dīn Chirāg-e Dehli, Amir Khusro, Maulāna Sharf al-Dīn, Maulāna Tāj al-Dīn, Qāḍī 'Abdu'l Muqtadir, Shaykh 'Alā al-Dīn Nilī and Burhān al-Dīn Gharīb also lived there.⁵ It was in 727/1327 that Syed Muḥammad Husainī accompanied his father to Daulatabād,⁷ which had just become the capital of the Tughlaq dynasty. A number of the disciples of Shaykh Nizām al-Dīn 'Auliya and Burhān al-Dīn Gharīb, had already preceded them there.⁸ It was in such an atmosphere of piety, learning and mysticism that he grew up. Abu'l Faiḍ Minallah Husainī⁹ states that his father Syed Yusuf used to spend most of his time at Daulatabād in the company of great saints like Shaykh Burhān al-Dīn Gharīb and Shaykh Bābu and it is most likely that Syed Muḥammad used to accompany his father in these visits. There is no doubt that he was with his father when the latter visited the famous saint Shaykh Bābu, who, seeing the young Syed Muḥammad, remarked, "I see in him the qualities of a scholar and a mystic."¹⁰

Syed Muḥammad Husainī had his early education under his maternal grandfather and studied *Nahw* in Arabic grammar as well as *Qudūrī* in jurisprudence¹¹ even as a child. In 731/1331 he lost his father¹² and a few years later in 735/1334 his mother decided to settle down in Delhi with her

children. Soon after reaching Delhi he, along with his brother Syed Chanda Husaini, became the disciple of Shaykh Naṣīr al-Dīn.¹³ The latter advised him to take up arduous practices involving long hours of prayers, meditations and *dhikr*, at the same time living an austere and ascetic life. He was also required by his *pīr* to continue his education in the traditional learning of Islam, which he did under the guidance of Syed Sharf al-Dīn Katheli, Maulāna Tāj al-Dīn and Qāḍī 'Abdu'l Muqtaḍir.¹⁴ As it was not possible to meditate with the high concentration prescribed by the tenets of his silsilah he found a peaceful room in *Ḥazīrah* of Shir Khān Jahān Panāh, where he continued to live for the next ten years.¹⁵ Shaykh Naṣīr al-Dīn once visited his young disciple in the *Ḥazīrah* and offered him a few coins by way of *nadhṛ*, which was most unusual on the part of a *pīr* and an unprecedented privilege to a *murīd*.¹⁶ Shaykh Naṣīr al-Dīn was very pleased with the rapid and remarkable progress made by his protegee' in the sufi path, which reminded him of similar attainments of the great saints in the past. It is likely that these events took place before 757/1356 as Shaykh Naṣīr al-Dīn honoured him with the *khilafat* in that year.¹⁷

Syed Muḥammad Husaini was only 36 years old when three days after the death of his *pīr* he assumed the high office of his *pīr's* successor and extended his hand for *baia'th*.¹⁸ At forty he got married at the instance of his mother and continued to deliver lectures and conduct discourses in his *khānqāh*. He always observed strictly the tenets of the *Sharī'ah* and Sāmāni reports that while he was still living in Delhi, the reputed scholar in exoteric knowledge, Maulāna Naṣīr al-Dīn Qasim, who had studied under Maulāna Mu'in al-Dīn 'Imrāni, became his disciple. When Mu'in al-Dīn 'Imrāni heard of this development he asked his student how a scholar like him could become a *murīd*. Maulāna Naṣīr al-Dīn replied that while he had become a scholar under him he actually became Muslim under Syed Muḥammad.¹⁹

Syed Muḥammad Husaini Gesūdarāz spent twenty-one years (736-757/1336-1356) as a disciple of his *pīr*, and forty-four years (757-801/1356-1398) as the spiritual successor of the latter at Delhi, and migrated to the Deccan in 801/1398 when he was 80 years old.²⁰ On his way he visited several places and finally arrived at Daulatabād in 803/1400 and at the request of Feroz Shāh Bahmani settled down in Gulbarga, the Bahmani capital. After spending twenty-two years he died there in 825/1425,²¹ where his mausoleum still stands.

On his arrival in Gulbarga he found the situation completely different from Delhi, as the king, Feroz Shāh Bahmani, like his ancestors, from the inception of the dynasty was in full sympathy with the sufis. This policy may not have been entirely disinterested and may have been influenced by the desire to win the support of religious leaders to his political aims. The king accorded Syed Muḥammad a royal welcome and constructed a *khānqāh* for him just opposite his palace outside the Gulbarga fort. While the early Chishti saints of the Deccan strictly observed the traditions of the silsila, Syed Muḥammad Husaini could not follow the same at Gulbarga.

Gesūdarāz as an scholar and author :

Syed Muhammad Husaini Gesūdarāz was an erudite scholar and a prolific writer. He was deeply versed in the Qur'ānic studies, in tradition, jurisprudence, theology and sufism.²² He had intensive knowledge of Arabic, Persian, Hindawi, Deccani and Sanskrit languages.²³ In one of his works he states that he had studied Sanskrit works and knew Hindu mythology.²⁴ Syed Muhammad Ḥusaini had made a thorough study of the following subjects :

- (a) *Tafsīr al-Kashshāf*—on the Qur'ān,
- (b) *Al-Hidāya*—on jurisprudence,
- (c) *Mashāriq al-Anwār*—on the Prophetic tradition,
- (d) *Uṣūl al-Bazdawī*—on jurisprudence,
- (e) *Mukhtaṣar al-Qudūrī*—on jurisprudence,
- (f) *Miftāh al-'Ulūm*—on philology,
- (g) *Kitāb al-Miṣbāh fī al-Naḥw*—on philology,
- (h) *Al-Kāfiyah*—on syntax,
- (i) *Al-Risālah al-Shamsiyah*—on logic.²⁵

Apart from these works he must necessarily have delved deeply in the sufi literature available in India at that time. This is supported by the fact that he himself compiled commentaries on many classical sufi works.²⁶ From this it obviously follows that the several sufi treatises available in India must have influenced his thought. Abu'l Qāsim al-Junaid (d. 298/910) of Baghdad seems to have been the model for Gesūdarāz. Besides him, he mentions several other sufis in his works like Najm al-Din Kubra, Jalāl al-Din Rūmi, Farid al-Din 'Aṭṭār and Ibn 'Arabi.²⁷ Although *Fuṣūṣ al-Ḥikam* of Muhiy al-Din ibn 'Arabi (d. 638/1240) immensely influenced his doctrines, nevertheless Gesūdarāz maintained a critical attitude towards Ibn 'Arabi's concept of ontological unity of All-being, (*Waḥdat al-Wajūd*).²⁸

In Gulbarga, Syed Muḥammad Ḥusaini established a *madrasa* for advanced learning at his *khānqāh*, in which education in various branches of Islamic thought was imparted not only to the elite of Gulbarga, but also to those coming from other parts of the Bahmani kingdom and from elsewhere in India.²⁹ Syed Muḥammad himself taught *Ḥadīth*, *Tafsīr*, *Sulūk*, *Kalām*, and *Fiqh* to his sons. Qaḍi Rāju and Shihāb al-Dīn also studied *Mulṭaqit* and *Qūtu'l Qulūb* under the saint. Maulāna Abu'l Faṭḥ along with Syed Aṣghar Ḥusaini and Syed Ahmed took lessons in the commentaries on various sufi tracts written by Gesūdarāz and Malikzāda 'Izz al-Dīn studied *'Adāb al-Murīdīn*. Syed Yadullah Ḥusaini took lessons in *Miṣbāh* and later on started studying *Kāfiyah*.³⁰ In 806/1403 Maulāna 'Alā al-Dīn came from Gwalior to study *Tamhidāt-e 'an al-Qudat* and *Fuṣūṣ al-Ḥikam* under Syed Muhammad Husaini.³¹ The way in which this institution was run and the knowledge which it spread were a source of pride and inspiration to the people and possibly engendered envy in the heart of the ruler of the state, as the ninety year old saint continued to win the hearts and minds of the people.

Mir Vali al-Din³² is of the opinion that Syed Muḥammad Ḥusaini was the first Chishti sufi who put the *Ilm-e Sina* (esoteric knowledge) into the *'Ilm-e*

Safina (exoteric knowledge). Our saint himself states, "Every one who traverses the path to God receives a particular gift: God has bestowed on me the gift of explaining His secrets."³³ At another place, he writes, "The qualities of a Jurist, Sufi, Syed and Sunni in their totality are found in very few persons: God has bestowed on me all these qualities."³⁴

According to one tradition, Syed Muḥammad Husaini was the author of one hundred and five works,³⁵ while Syed Minallah³⁶ is of the opinion that he wrote one hundred and twenty-five works. His biographers Sāmānī³⁷ and Wā'izī³⁸ have listed thirty-six and forty-seven books, respectively. As a large number of his works are available either in manuscript or in published form in various libraries of India and London, it is obvious that the list given by his biographers is incomplete. However, it is difficult to ascertain the exact number of works written by him and the following are some of his more important treatises:

- I. EXEGESIS: (i) *Tafsīr-e Multaqīt.*
(ii) *Hawāshi-e Kashshāf.*
- II. HADITH: (i) *Sharḥ-e Mashāriq al-Anwār.*
(ii) *A Persian translation of Mashāriq.*
- III. FIQH: (i) *Sharḥ al-Fiqh al-Akbar.*
- IV. TASAWWUF: (i) *Sharḥ-e 'Awārif al-Ma'ārif* (Arabic and Persian)
(ii) *Sharḥ-e Ta'arruf.*
(iii) *Sharḥ-e Ādāb al-Murīdīn.* (Arabic)
(iv) *Ādāb al-Murīdīn.*
(v) *Fuṣūṣ al-Hikam.*
(vi) *Sharḥ-e Tamhidāt.* (Persian)
(vii) *Sharḥ-e Risālah-e Qushayrīyah* (Persian & Arabic)
(viii) *Hawāshi-e Qūtu'l-Qulūb.*
(ix) *Hazā'ir al-Quds or 'Ishq Nama.*
(x) *Jawāher al-'Ushshāq.*
(xi) *Athmār al-Asrār.*
(xii) *Khātima.*
(xiii) *Maktūbāt.*
(xiv) *Majmu'a-e Yāzdah Rasā'il.*
(xv) *Siyar al-Nabi.*
(xvi) *Anīs al-'Ushshāq.*
(xvii) *Malfūzāt*—Sāmānī mentions four *Malfūzāt*. But only one, compiled by his eldest son Syed Akber Husaini under the title *Jawāmi' al-Kalim*, exists.³⁹

Two more works in Deccani language *Mi'rāj al-'Ashiqīn* and *Shikār Nāma* are also attributed to him but there is no convincing evidence to establish that these were actually written by him.⁴⁰

Although most of Syed Muḥammad Husaini's works are in the form of commentaries, one cannot underrate the originality of his thought, particularly

his unique attempt at all times to bridge the gulf between the *Sharī'a* and the *Tariqah*, which existed at the time as a consequence of the age-old differences between the *Ahl-e Sharī'at* and the *Ahl-e Tariqat*, which prevailed throughout the Islamic world and which had acquired more emphasis in India.

Gesudarāz and Feroz Shah Bahmanī:

While 'Alā al-Dīn Hasan Bahman Shāh was the founder of the Bahmani dynasty which was established in 747/1347,⁴¹ his successors Muḥammad Shāh I, Feroz Shāh and Aḥmad Shāh Wali Bahmani were the founders and organisers of its social and religious institutions.⁴² Both the founder of the kingdom and his immediate successor had profound respect for the sufis and had ardent affection and respect for Shaykh Sirāj al-Dīn Junaidi, Shaykh Zain al-Dīn Daulatabādi and 'Ain al-Dīn Ganj al-'Ilm (treasury of knowledge). These sufis played a significant part in the political, religious and cultural life of the early Bahmani period.⁴³

Feroz Shāh Bahmani, eighth in the line of the Bahmani rulers, ruled for twenty-five years (800-825/1397-1424)⁴⁴ and it was in this period that Syed Muḥammad Husaini Gesudarāz lived twenty-three years of his life in the capital of the Bahmani kingdom, Gulbarga. It was also during this time that a large number of immigrants from Persia, Iraq and Iran made their way to the Deccan, as is evident from family names like Sīstāni, Tabrīzī, Māzandarāni and Kirmāni.⁴⁵ After ascending the throne, Feroz Shāh conferred the title of *Khān-e Khānān* on his younger brother Ahmad Khan, appointed Mir Faḍlu'llah Inju as *Wakil us-Saltanat*, and Maulāna Luṭfullah Shīrāzi as *Nā'ib Wakil us-Saltanat*.⁴⁶

The king like his predecessors had profound respect for sufis, scholars and men of high intellectual calibre and was himself a profound scholar. He was keenly interested in the problems of *Fiqh*, both *Shia'* and *Sunnī*, and subjects like *Qur'ān*, *Tafsīr*, *Ḥadīth* and *Kalām*. He respected also other religions and had read Old Testament as well as New Testament.⁴⁷ He had sound knowledge of Arabic, Persian, Turkish, Kanari, Marathi, Gujrati, Bengali and Telugu languages.⁴⁸ It was the ruler's broad outlook in all matters and his desire to have eminent scholars around him that attracted the 'ulama of Iran and Iraq like Maulāna Luṭf al-Dīn Sabzwāri, Hakīm Hasan Gilāni, Syed Muḥammad Garzūni and other learned men to his kingdom.⁴⁹

Feroz Shāh's inclination towards Shi'ism is evident from the adoption of the concept of *Muti'a* as suggested by Mir Faḍlu'llah Inju, against the advice of the Sunni 'ulama at his court.⁵⁰ He was the first Bahmani sultan to give his daughter in marriage to Shams al-Dīn Muḥammad Inju, who was later appointed governor of Daulatabād.⁵¹ Accordingly, it is difficult to find out what he felt about the *Ahl-e Sharī'at* or the *Ahl-e Tariqat* but there is no doubt that the immigrants from Iran and Iraq, the majority of whom were Shi'ites, did influence his thought profoundly.

It is difficult to find out the exact reasons which prompted the king to invite the saint to settle down permanently in his kingdom. It is quite

possible that the extraordinary popularity which the saint enjoyed with his subjects may have influenced him and it is also possible that by this time he may have become tired of the endless disputes and rivalries of the *Sunni* and *Shia* 'ulama at his court. These experiences might have caused him to yearn for a personality far above such petty and trivial differences, who combined in himself the whole range of the esoteric and the exoteric knowledge with the deep insight and compassion of a mystic of the eminence of Syed Muḥammad Ḥusainī.

The king extended a warm welcome which drew them closer to each other and inspired mutual confidence. However, this did not last long and the relations became more strained in the subsequent years, possibly for several reasons, one being the wide and unprecedented popularity of the saint among the people, which might have made the king apprehensive; the sharp differences between the *Ahl-e Shari'at* and *Ahl-e Tariqat* and the not inconsiderable influence which the *Shī'a* 'ulama exercised on the king may have been a contributory factor. Sāmānī reports an incident which helps one in understanding this change in the attitude of the king towards the saint.

He states that Maulāna 'Alā al-Dīn Gawāliari came to Gulbarga in 806/1403 to take lessons in *Fuṣūṣ al-Hikam* of Ibn 'Arabi from Gesūdarāz and this gave the 'ulama, who had profound antagonism towards Ibn 'Arabi, a chance to persuade the king to find out how Syed Muḥammad Ḥusainī explained the deviations of Ibn 'Arabi's thought from *Sharia*.⁵² Feroz Shah deputed Khwaja Ahmad Dabir, a trusted and learned scholar of his court, to enquire from the saint what he thought of the matter under dispute, but instead of submitting his report to the king, Ahmad Dabir became the disciple of the saint and probably resigned from the court service. This might have irked Feroz Shāh and alienated him from the saint. The antagonism between the two in its early stages was purely on an intellectual plane and the formal relations between the two continued to be marked by mutual respect until 810/1407.⁵³ In that year Feroz Shāh marched against Vijayanagar and achieved a glorious victory, which resulted in a long era of peace between the two kingdoms and in a matrimonial alliance. This produced a feeling of superiority and pride in the mind of the king. At first irked by the tremendous popularity of the saint which made vast crowds gather around him, the king issued an order to the saint to change his residence to some place outside the city as the noise created by the large concourse of people was a source of disturbance to him. The saint immediately complied with the king's order and moved to the place where his tomb now stands. Most of the historians of the Bahmani period associate this change in his place of residence with the event of the coronation ceremony of Ḥasan Khān, the king's eldest son, in 818/1415.⁵⁴ In view of the facts stated above Syed Muḥammad Ḥusainī must have changed his place of residence between 810/1407 and 812/1409. One external evidence of this change is the death of the saint's eldest son, Syed Akber Ḥusainī, in 812/1408.⁵⁵ The shrine of the latter stands exactly opposite to the shrine of Syed Muḥammad Ḥusainī.⁵⁶

In 818/1415 Feroz Shāh appointed his son Ḥasan Khān as his heir-apparent and after the formal coronation ceremony sent the prince to call on

Syed Muḥammad Ḥusainī for the latter's blessings. The saint on receiving the prince remarked, "The crown was decreed to descend to his brother Ahmad Khan by the will of Providence; it was in vain for him to bestow it on another."⁵⁷ Thus not only did the saint refuse to accept the king's choice of the heir-apparent but actually preferred another member of the royal family for the honour. This reflects the serious differences between the spiritual leadership and the temporal power.

In course of time a very close and intimate relationship seems to have developed between Ahmad Khān and the saint, Syed Muḥammad Ḥusainī. In 820/1417⁵⁸ Feroz Shāh again invaded Vijayanagar, much against the wishes of the saint, and was badly defeated and it was only Ahmad Khān who finally succeeded in driving out the Vijayanagar army from the kingdom. This must have further helped Ahmad Khān in his bid for the throne. Soon after this the nobles of the court reminded the king of the close and intimate relations between Ahmad Khān and the saint and Feroz Shāh remembering the prediction of the saint, ordered his brother to be blinded.⁵⁹ On hearing this, Ahmad Khān along with his son 'Alā-al-Dīn rushed to the *khānqāh* of the saint for succour. On seeing the two the saint removed the turban from 'Ala al-Dīn's head and divided it into two. One-half he tied on Ahmad's head and the other half on the head of 'Ala al-Dīn and then extending his hand over them predicted sovereignty to both.⁶⁰ The royal army sent in pursuit of the two was defeated by Ahmad Khān with the help of Khalaf Ḥasan Baṣari and the former assumed kingship.⁶¹ A few months later both Feroz Shāh and Syed Muḥammad Ḥusaini died.

Deviations from Chishti Traditions :

Syed Muḥammad Ḥusaini Gesūdarāz during his stay of twenty-three years in Gulbarga devoted most of his energy to the establishment and organization of the Chishti order in the Deccan. The character of the *khānqāh* which became active with the establishment of the Bahmani kingdom, especially during the first phase, culminating in the death of Gesūdarāz, is in sharp contrast to its earlier character and its role in North India, which was passive vis-a-vis the state. The *khānqāh* in the Deccan became highly active under the early sufis of the Deccan and Syed Muḥammad Ḥusaini.⁶² The change implied a clear deviation from the established traditions of the early Chishtis.⁶³ The most plausible factor might be the new situation with which the sufis and the rulers had to deal in the Deccan. The Bahmani rulers appeared to be apprehensive about the security of their newly established empire during the first fifty years and in order to secure mass support of their subjects, had to seek the backing of the sufis, while the latter saw in this an opportunity of achieving their social and religious goal through the patronage of the kings.

Another important deviation within the *khānqāh* institution which came to surface in this period was in respect of the issue of spiritual succession. The history of the Chishti order from its inception in India shows that none of the early Shaykhs right upto Shaykh Nasir al-Dīn Chirāgh of Delhi ever nominated any of their family members as their spiritual successor.⁶⁴ Syed

Muhammad Husaini, however left a will appointing one of his sons as his successor, thus making the succession hereditary.⁶⁵

Syed Ali Tabatabā'i⁶⁶ and other authors⁶⁷ clearly state that Feroz Shāh Bahmani, on Gesūdarāz's arrival in Gulbarga, presented him *jāgirs* by way of *nadh*r through an official farman,⁶⁸ but there is a difference of opinion whether the saint accepted these *jāgirs* or not. Wā'izi⁶⁹ categorically states that the saint did not accept the king's gift and said :

“Our Shaykhs did not accept any such income, I too shall not accept.”

Wā'izi further states that the saint once remarked :

“I do not want that my sons, relatives and friends bring any part of such income to me.”

It is also said that the saint often spoke against persons who accepted royal bounty and never consented to accept a part of such income.⁷⁰ However, his sons and grandsons later accepted a large number of such grants in the shape of *jāgirs* and cash grants.⁷¹

Institutions after his death :

Soon after the saint's death the splendid intellectual and spiritual edifice developed during his stay in Gulbarga started disintegrating. There were many reasons for this, perhaps the most important being the controversy started by the family members to be the heads of the order (*sajjāda nashīn*) and the acceptance of *jāgirs*, cash grants, royal titles, etc. by the sons and grandsons of Gesūdarāz. Syed Ali Tabatbā'i⁷² specifically states that after the death of the saint, Ahmed Shah Wali Bahmani did not have any faith in the *Mashā'iqs* of the Deccan and hence he did not have any liking for them. The events relating to the spiritual succession soon after the death of the saint not only damaged the prestige and image of the family in the contemporary society, but the sultan lost all hopes in the spiritual attainments of the successors of Gesūdarāz. The latter's basic concept of spiritual pursuits was replaced, soon after his death by the mundane desires of his descendants for acquisition of *jāgirs* and other worldly possessions and there was not one among them who could match the high intellectual or spiritual attainments of our saint or his eldest son, Syed Akber Husainī with the inevitable result that the institution which he had done so much to set up, soon lost all hopes of ever gaining the popularity which it once enjoyed.

REFERENCES

- (1) 'Abdul 'Aziz Wā'izī, *Tārikh-e Ḥabībī*, Hyderabad, 1368 A.H. pp. 7, 8.
- (2) Syed Minallah. *Tabṣīratu'l-Khawariqāt*, Hyderabad, 1966, pp. 6, 7. Ashraf Jahangir Samnānī, *Maktūbat*, MSS. Raoḍ-e Buzarg Collection, Gulbarga, Letter No. 32, f. 117. 'Abdul Haq, *Akhhār al-Akhyār*, Urdu trans., A. Nizami, Delhi, n. d. p. 237.
- (3) Muḥammad 'Ali Sāmānī, *Siyar-e Muḥammadī*, Hyderabad, 1949, p. 12.
- (4) *Ibid.* p. 3.

- (6) K. A. Nizami, 'Sufi movements in the Deccan,' *History of Medieval Deccan (1295-1724)* Edt. H. K. Sberwani and P. M. Joshi, Hyderabad, 1974, Vol. II, pp. 179, 180.
- (7) There is a difference of opinion among his biographers regarding the date of his first visit to Daulatabād. Syed Minallah states that he left Delhi on 30th Ramaḍān, 725 A.H. and reached Daulatabād on 7th Muharram, 726 A.H. Sāmāni only states that he was in his fourth year. Maulāna 'Abdu'l 'Azīz states that his father left Delhi for Daulatabād because of the change of capital, which took place in 727/1327. 'Abdu'l 'Azīz sounds more correct to me. Syed Minallah, *op. cit.*, p. 101. Sāmāni, *op. cit.*, p. 8. 'Abdu'l 'Azīz, *op. cit.*, p. 8.
- (8) Prominent among the disciples of Shaykh Nizām al-Dīn 'Auliya were, Amir Hasan 'Ala Sijzi, author of *Fawā'idul-Fu'ad*, Shaykh Kamal Khujandi, Shaykh Fakhr al-Dīn, Pir Mubarak Kārwan, Khwaja Hasan, Khwaja 'Umar, Kamal al Dīn Sāmāna and Syed Yusuf al-Ḥusaini. Prominent among the disciples of Shaykh Burhān al-Dīn Gharib were Kāka Sa'd Bakhsh, Syed Naṣīr al-Dīn Paonpek, Rukn al-Dīn bin 'Imād al-Dīn Dabīr Kāshāni, author of *Shamā'ilu'l-Atqia* and other works and Shaykh Zain al-Dīn Shirāzi Daulatabādi.
- (9) Abu'l Faīd Minallah Ḥusaini, *Shawāmilu'l-Jumal fī Shamā'ilu'l-Kumal*, MSS. 170 A.H. Raoḍa-e Shaykh collection, Gulbarga, p. 49.
- (10) *Ibid.*, Syed Minallah, *op. cit.*, p. 74. Later authors are of the opinion that Shaykh Bābu was a saint of Suhrawardi silsila, Raonaq Ali, *Raoḍatu'l Aqṭab*, Aurangabad, 1320 A.H. p. 74.
- (11) Sāmāni, *op. cit.*, pp. 11, 12.
- (12) Raonaq 'Ali, *op. cit.*, p. 74.
- (13) Sāmāni, *op. cit.* p. 15. For a short biographical notice see Hamid Qalander, *Khairu'l Majālis*, MSS. dated 1313 A.H. State Library, Hyd. K. A. Nizami, *Some Aspects of Religion and Politics in India during 13th century, Bombay 1961*. K. A. Nizami, *Tarikh-e Mashā'iq-e Chisht*, Delhi, 1953.
- (14) Sāmāni, *op. cit.*, pp. 13, 14, 15.
- (15) *Ibid.*, p. 19.
- (16) *Ibid.*, p. 20.
- (17) *Ibid.*, pp. 25, 26, 27. Wā'izī, *op. cit.* p. 15. There exists a controversy on the issue of *khilāfat*. Prof. K. A. Nizami is of the opinion that Shaykh Naṣīr al-Dīn did not bestow *khilāfat* upon any one till his death. He has based his opinion on a supplement found in *Khairu'l-Majālis*, *Malfuzat* of the Shaykh, compiled by one of his disciples Ḥamid Qalander. But other contemporary sources of the time of Gesūdarāz state about his appointment as the *khalīfah*.
- (18) Sāmāni, *op. cit.*, pp. 31, 32.
- (19) *Ibid.*, pp. 78, 79.

- (20) There is a difference of opinion among the scholars on the date of his arrival at Gulbarga. Different authors have given different dates. Muḥammad Qāsim Ferishta states that he arrived in 815/1415. Bilgrami gives 805/1405. Syed Minallah gives the following couplet, which gives the exact year of his arrival :

دو سال و بست در گاہر گہ بودند در کشف و گرامت را کشودند

- (21) Sāmānī, *op. cit.*, pp. 91, 95.
 (22) *Ibid.*, pp. 91, 95. Wā'izi, *op. cit.*, pp. 85, 125.
 (23) K.A. Nizami, Gesūdarāz, *Encyclopaedia of Islam*, p. 1115.
 (24) Syed Minallah, *op. cit.*, pp. 11, 12, 13. Muhammad Mujeeb, *Indian Muslims*, London, 1967, p. 165.
 (25) Syed Shah Khusro Ḥusaini, *Syed Muhammad al-Ḥusaini Gesūdarāz, 721-825/1321-1422 on Sufism*, Thesis, McGill University, 1976, pp. 22, 23.
 (26) Sāmānī, *op. cit.*, pp. 114, 115. Wā'izi, *op. cit.*, pp. 65, 66, 67.
 (27) Ḥusainī, *op. cit.*, pp. 24, 25.
 (28) *Ibid.*
 (29) Sāmānī, *op. cit.*, pp. 98, 99.
 (30) *Ibid.*, p. 99.
 (31) *Ibid.*, p. 57.
 (32) Mir Vali al-Dīn, *Khwaja Band-i-Nawaz and his Contribution to Sufism*, Hyderabad, n. d. preface, p. 1.
 (33) Gesūdarāz, *Athmār al-Asrar*, ed. 'Atā Ḥusain, Hyderabad, 1350 A.H., Intd. p. 1.
 (34) Wā'izī, *op. cit.*, p. 36.
 (35) K.A. Nizami, *op. cit.*, p. 1115.
 (36) Syed Minallah, *op. cit.*, p. 120.
 (37) Sāmānī, *op. cit.*, pp. 114, 115, 116.
 (38) Wā'izi, *op. cit.*, pp. 64-67.
 (39) Sāmānī, *op. cit.*, pp. 114, 115. Wā'izi, *op. cit.*, pp. 66, 67.
 (40) K.A. Nizami, *op. cit.*, p. 1115.
 (41) Syed Ali Tabatabā'i, *Burhān-e-Ma'aṣir*, Ed. G. Yazdani, Hyderabad, 1938, p. 15. Briggs, *History of the Rise of Muhammadan Power in India*, London, 1829, Vol. 11, p. 440.
 (42) H.K. Sherwani, *Bahmanis of the Deccan*, Hyderabad, 1953, p. 77.
 (43) Muhammad Suleman Siddiqi, *Sufis of the Deccan, 1347-1538 A.D.*, Ph.D. Thesis, 1975, O.U., Chapter IV.
 (44) Briggs, *op. cit.*, p. 362.
 (45) *Ibid.*, p. 148.

- (46) *Ibid.*, p. 370. Tabatabā'i, *op. cit.*, p. 41. M.J.S. King, *The History of the Bahmani Dynasty*, London, 1900, p. 38. 'Abdu'l Majeed Siddiqi, Art. Mir Fazlullah Inju, *Islamic Culture*, April, 1948, pp. 165-174.
- (47) Briggs, *op. cit.*, p. 338. Tabatabā'i, *op. cit.*, pp. 48, 52. Bilgrami, *Raḍātu'l 'Auliya*, Aurangabad, 1310 A.H., p. 39.
- (48) Briggs, *op. cit.*, p. 389. Also see Tabatabā'i, *op. cit.*, p. 52. Maulavi Zaheer al-Dīn, *Sultan Ahmed Shah Bahmani*, Hyderabad, 1940, pp. 10-20.
- (49) Briggs, *op. cit.*, p. 338. Tabatabā'i, *op. cit.*, pp. 48, 52.
- (50) Briggs, *op. cit.*, p. 364.
- (51) *Ibid.*, p. 369.
- (52) Sāmānī, *op. cit.*, p. 57.
- (53) H.K. Sherwani, *op. cit.*, pp. 161, 162.
- (54) Briggs, *op. cit.*, p. 389. Tabatabā'i, *op. cit.*, p. 48.
- (55) Sāmānī, *op. cit.*, p. 143. Wā'izi, *op. cit.*, p. 56. Syed Minallah, *op. cit.*, p. 115.
- (56) There was a tradition among the Chishti saints that they were usually buried at the place of their residence. The later authors also state that Syed Muḥammad Ḥusainī personally used to supervise the construction of the shrine of his son. One must note that the saint was then in his nineties. It is difficult to believe that the saint used to come all the way from his old *khānqāh* every day to supervise the work, in view of the fact that the saint could hardly walk during his late age, as stated by Abu'l Faiḍ Minallah Ḥusainī, the grandson of the saint in his work *Shawāmilu'l-Jumal fī Shamai'lu'l Kumal*.
- (57) Briggs, *op. cit.*, p. 389.
- (58) *Ibid.* Syed Minallah, *op. cit.*, p. 94.
- (59) Briggs, *op. cit.*, pp. 389, 390.
- (60) *Ibid.*
- (61) Tabatabā'i, *op. cit.*, p. 48. H.K. Sherwani, *op. cit.*, p. 167.
- (62) For sufi-state relationship see: Muhammad Suleman Siddiqi, *op. cit.* Chapters four to six.
- (63) K A. Nizāmi, *Some Aspects of Religion and Politics in India during the 13th century*, Bombay, 1961, p. 250.
- (64) *Ibid.*, K A. Nizāmi, *Tārīkh-e Mashā'iq-e Chishti*, Delhi, 1953, pp. 200-208.
- (65) There are two wills (*waṣī'at-namas*) of Gesūdarāz, one in favour of his grandson Syed Shāh Safirullah Ḥusainī and the other in favour of his younger son Syed Shah Asgharu'llah Ḥusainī. Wā'izī, *op. cit.*, p. 50. Syed Minallah, *op. cit.*, p. 111. See also document of Mahmood Shah Bahmani and the document *Ahednama*, Raḍī-e Buzarg collection, Gulbarga. For document also see Muhammad Suleman Siddiqi, *op. cit.*, Appendix, B-4, B-5.
- (66) Tabatabā'i, *op. cit.*, p. 48.

- (67) Muhammad Qasim Ferishta, *op. cit.*, p. 180. K. A. Nizami, Sufi movements in the Deccan, *History of the Medieval Deccan*, Vol. II, p. 185.
- (68) This Farman is extinct.
- (69) Wā'izi, *op. cit.*, p. 92.
- (70) *Ibid.*
- (71) Jahan Numā 'Alī Shah, *Tarikh-e Muhammadiā*, Hyderabad, 1318, A.H. pp. 71-75.
- (72) Tabatabā'i, *op. cit.*, p. 54.

[And say : My Lord ! Increase me in knowledge—Qur'ān]

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